

REVIEWS ON THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN HEAT EXPOSURE AND PERINATAL HEALTH OUTCOMES

Deliverable number D2.7

Updated systematic review 2

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.7

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	Reviews on the association between heat exposure and perinatal health outcomes* *Original title: Updated systematic review 2
Deliverable number	D2.7
WP number	WP2
Author(s)	Darshnika P Lakhoo (Wits PHR) and Eline Holvoet (UGent), for the HIGH Horizons Study Group <i>Updated systematic (review #1):</i> Darshnika P Lakhoo, Ijeoma Solarin, Shobna Sawry, Nandi Mwase, Natasha Lalloo, Mags Beksinska, Jean le Roux, Sibusiso Mkwanzani, Ursula Gazeley, Kennedy Otwombe, Khuthadzo Hlongwane, Nicholas Brink, Matthew Chersich, Lebohang Radebe <i>Scoping review (review #2):</i> Eline Holvoet, Paul Lokubal, Darshnika Lakhoo, Veronique Filippi, Shobna Sawry, Matthew Chersich, Debra Jackson, Stanley Luchters
Lead beneficiary	Wits Health Consortium (Wits PHR & Wits RHI), UGent and LSHTM
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Due date	31 August 2025

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Structure, methods and results completed (31 July 2025)
Version 1.0	Final and approved report (30 August 2025)

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HIGH Horizons project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the European Commission or UKRI. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission and UKRI are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. This document and its content are the property of the HIGH Horizons Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HIGH Horizons project and the document are properly referenced. Each HIGH Horizons Partner may use this document in conformity with the HIGH Horizons Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

Table of Contents

- List of tables 4
- List of figures 4
- List of acronyms 4
- Executive summary 5
- 1 Introduction 6
- 2 Background 7
- 3 REVIEW #1: Updated systematic review on high temperature exposure in pregnancy and adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes 8
 - 3.1 Context 8
 - 3.2 Methods..... 9
 - 3.3 Results 9
 - 3.4 Discussion 13
- 4 REVIEW #2: Scoping review on heat and neonatal health outcomes 15
 - 4.1 Methods..... 15
 - 4.2 Results 19
 - 4.3 Discussion 22
- 5 Conclusion 23
- 6 Appendices 24
 - 6.1 Appendix A: Study references of review #1 24
 - 6.2 Appendix B: Study references of review #2..... 26
- 7 References 34

List of tables

Table 1. Review #1: Distribution of studies across location and income level of country	11
Table 2. Review #2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria used for screening	17
Table 3. Review #2: Charting form for data extraction for the scoping review	19
Table 4. Review #2: Distribution of studies across location and time	21
Table 5. Review #1: References included in the updated systematic review of heat and maternal and neonatal health outcomes.....	24
Table 6. Review #2: References included in the scoping review of heat and neonatal health outcomes.....	26

List of figures

Figure 1. Review #1: PRISMA flow diagram representing the results of the screening process.....	10
Figure 2. Review #1: Tree map showing distribution of study themes.....	12
Figure 3. Review #1: Vote counting representing direction of effect.....	12
Figure 4. Review #2: PRISMA flow diagram representing the results of the screening process.....	20

List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
JBI	Joanna Briggs Institute
LMIC	Low- and middle-income country
MeSH	Medical subject heading
MNH	Maternal and newborn health
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PRISMA-ScR	PRISMA extension for scoping reviews

Executive summary

The HIGH Horizons project addresses the growing concern over the adverse effects of heat exposure on maternal and newborn health, including outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirth, and contributed to the evidence-base by conducting major literature reviews. Building on the 2020 systematic review by Chersich et al., the HIGH Horizons team conducted a first comprehensive update about the impact of heat on perinatal health outcomes, published in Nature Medicine in November 2024. A second update, presented in this report, was conducted in December 2024 to extend the evidence period with several months. This update notably increased representation from Asia and Africa and from lower-income settings, addressing key gaps in geographic and socioeconomic diversity. It also reaffirmed strong associations between heat exposure and adverse maternal and newborn health outcomes, particularly preterm birth, stillbirth, hypertensive disorders, and low birth weight. This last systematic review update was complemented by a scoping review which focused on the effects of heat on neonatal health and identified similar concerns such as preterm birth, low birth weight and small for gestational age. Nearly 90% of the studies in the scoping review were published post-2020, reflecting the increased interest in this research area.

1 Introduction

The adverse effects of heat exposure on maternal and newborn health outcomes (MNH) such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirth are confirmed by many studies. The HIGH Horizons project was conceptualised around these findings, with the aim to reduce or avoid the adverse health effects by a set of adaptation interventions, not only for pregnant and postpartum women but also for health workers whose productivity, wellbeing and quality of care are affected by heat exposure. The feasibility and cost-effectiveness of the adaptation interventions in health facilities in South Africa, Sweden and Zimbabwe are studied and described in other deliverables^a, but because the heat-MNH knowledge base would grow during the implementation of the HIGH Horizons project, we considered to update the systematic review on associations between high temperatures in pregnancy and perinatal health outcomes, published by Chersich (one of the HIGH Horizons research designers) and colleagues in 2020.¹ The update would use the same two-stage review process to sum any new evidence on heat impacts on MNH and relevant adaptation-mitigation interventions. A first thorough update was made in February 2024 in [deliverable D2.6 - Updated systematic review](#), resulting in a [publication in Nature Medicine](#).^{2,3} A second and last update of the systematic review is made below (review #1), and complemented by a (non-planned) scoping review focusing on adverse neonatal health outcomes (review #2).

^a The HIGH Horizons website ([Publications – HIGH Horizons](#)) has an overview of all deliverables by objective, including the objective related to the heat adaptation interventions. Deliverables which have been approved are also uploaded in the Zenodo community of HIGH Horizons ([Search HIGH Horizons](#)).

2 Background

The rapid advancement of climate change is now recognised as one of the most pressing global health challenges of the 21st century.⁴ An estimated 1.2 billion vulnerable individuals could be exposed to extreme heat annually if the global average temperature rises by 1.5°C.⁴ In 2023 alone, extreme heat was estimated to cause approximately 48,000 deaths across Europe.⁵ Rising heat-related death rates are expected to further intensify existing health disparities and social inequalities, disproportionately affecting marginalised populations, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) and urban environments.^{6,7,8,9} Importantly, those most affected by climate change are often the least responsible for greenhouse gas emissions and are frequently underrepresented in both research and policy discussions.⁸

As global temperatures continue to climb, the burden of heat-related illness and mortality is projected to increase, especially among high-risk groups such as neonates.^{4,10} Due to their immature thermoregulatory systems and high surface-area-to-mass ratio, neonates—especially those born preterm or with low birth weight—are physiologically vulnerable to ambient heat.^{11,12,13} Neonatal morbidity and mortality risks are further increased in the presence of complications affecting either the neonate—such as prematurity, low birth weight, infections, or congenital anomalies—or the mother, including hypertensive disorders like preeclampsia or obstructed labour.^{3,14,15}

The biological mechanisms linking heat exposure to adverse neonatal outcomes remain underexplored. Potential pathways include maternal hyperthermia leading to foetal distress, increased inflammatory responses, altered placental function, and dehydration.^{16,17} Furthermore, thermal instability post-birth may contribute to neonatal complications such as seizures, jaundice, and dehydration.³ Nevertheless, current neonatal guidelines focus primarily on hypothermia prevention, with insufficient protocols for managing hyperthermia risks.¹²

Considering the accelerating climate crisis and the increasing frequency of extreme heat events, it is essential to assess these risks promptly to guide future research and strengthen health system preparedness.

3 REVIEW #1: Updated systematic review on high temperature exposure in pregnancy and adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes

3.1 Context

In the published systematic review and meta-analysis of heat impacts on maternal, foetal, and neonatal health, we quantified the impacts and showcased the breadth of impacts across 23 outcomes and 66 countries.^{2,3} By far, the most evidence was available for heat impacts on neonatal health outcomes, particularly preterm birth and low birth weight, both crucial determinants of child mortality, health, and wellbeing over the life course. Five critical outcomes - preterm births, low birth weight, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, congenital anomalies, and stillbirths accounted for 75% of the evidence. Ten outcomes, however, including several major causes of maternal mortality, were represented by only one or two publications, constraining our ability to summarise the full extent of heat harms in these populations. LMICs were poorly represented in the data, as were analyses from countries with high mean temperatures and tropical climate zones. A significant proportion, 94% of the studies - were published after 2000, highlighting the rapid increase in publications in this field.

Considering this, we sought to update the review to reflect the current body of literature. We aim to guide further research, indicator development and to catalyse policy reforms focused on mitigating the impacts of heat on these vulnerable populations.

3.2 Methods

The methods for this updated systematic review remain unchanged from the initial systematic review.^{2,3} The same information sources, search strategy, selection process and data extraction process were applied.

We conducted a systematic review following the 2020 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines.¹⁸ Included were all peer-reviewed epidemiological studies assessing the impact of heat during pregnancy on maternal and neonatal outcomes. We conducted the updated search in December 2024, to include an additional 17 months of evidence.

For this updated systematic review, no meta-analysis was conducted. Updated results have been synthesised and are summarised below. Findings are interpreted in relation to the original systematic review.

3.3 Results

We screened an additional 2,337 records, of which 43 were included for full text review. Following full text review, an additional 12 studies were excluded based on ineligible outcomes of interest (n=10), animal study (n=1) and qualitative study design (n=1) (Figure 1). Overall, this resulted in an additional 31 studies that met the inclusion criteria.

The list of these 31 studies is included in Appendix A.

Figure 1. Review #1: PRISMA flow diagram representing the results of the screening process

The studies spanned across 38 locations and 21 countries (Table 1). The 38 locations were predominantly based in Asia (45%), followed by Africa (24%), and Europe, North America and Australia with 11% each. Most studies were in high income countries (39%), followed by upper-middle income (26%), lower-middle income (24%), and low income countries (11%).

Table 1. Review #1: Distribution of studies across location and income level of country

	Categories	Number of records	Percentage (%)
Location of study (continent)*	Asia	17	45
	Africa	9	24
	Europe	4	11
	North America	4	11
	Australia	4	11
Income level of country*	High	15	39
	Upper middle	10	26
	Lower middle	9	24
	Low	4	11

Note: *Varying totals due to multi-site, multi-country and multiple continents for individual studies and multiple outcomes and population groups per study.

The study outcomes were grouped into 19 different themes. The most commonly studied outcome was preterm birth (n=18), followed by stillbirth (n=8), hypertension in pregnancy (n=7), and low birth weight (n=6) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Review #1: Tree map showing distribution of study themes

When analysing the vote counting results, most studies had outcomes that showed a harmful effect of temperature (Figure 3). There is some heterogeneity for results in stillbirths, small for gestational age and hypertension in pregnancy. Neonatal morbidity studies all showed heat as a protective exposure.

Figure 3. Review #1: Vote counting representing direction of effect

3.4 Discussion

There has been continuation in the rapidly growing body of literature on the impacts of heat on maternal, neonatal and foetal health. The updated search, which screened 2,337 and included 31 new studies, expands the scope of the first updated review in important ways.

While the original body of evidence was dominated by high income countries (63%) and temperate climate zones, the updated search identified proportionally more studies from Asia and Africa (45% and 24% respectively), and a larger share of studies conducted in lower middle and low income settings (24% and 11%, respectively, compared with only 3% previously). This shift strengthens the geographic and socioeconomic diversity of the evidence base, beginning to address an important research gap noted in the earlier review.

In terms of outcomes, the newly added studies continued to focus most heavily on neonatal health, particularly preterm birth (n=18 in the updated search), reinforcing this as the most consistently studied outcome. Stillbirths (n=8),

hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (n=7), and low birth weight (n=6) were also prominent in the additional literature, aligning with the key outcome categories previously identified. However, the updated studies also broadened the scope of enquiry by examining additional outcomes such as birth anthropometry and early term birth. There is no new literature on antenatal or postnatal bleeding and mental health, and only one study on infections, despite these being major contributors to maternal mortality, with plausible links to heat.

The persistence of heterogeneity in some outcomes (e.g. stillbirth, small for gestational age, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy), and the protective effect of neonatal morbidity, not noted in the previous review update, highlights the ongoing methodological challenges in exposure definitions, outcome classification, and contextual variability.

The updated evidence reinforces the overall conclusions of the original review, that heat exposure during pregnancy is consistently associated with increased risk of adverse maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes, while also beginning to fill some of the critical geographic, socioeconomic and outcome gaps identified previously. This evidence strengthens the known risks to these vulnerable groups, across varied contexts, and that policy actions are needed urgently to mitigate the impacts of heat exposure.

4 **REVIEW #2: Scoping review on heat and neonatal health outcomes**

Because we were invited to write a review article for a peer-reviewed journal, we also conducted a scoping review to synthesise the up-to-date evidence on the relationship between heat exposure and neonatal health outcomes. The methods and preliminary results are described below. The article is expected to be published by the end of 2025.

4.1 **Methods**

4.1.1 **Eligibility criteria**

This scoping review was conducted following the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews^b and is reported in line with PRISMA-ScR guidelines.¹⁹ We focused on studies of neonates, defined as infants in the first 28 days of life. Studies were included if they reported on neonatal-specific health outcomes within the neonatal period. Broader perinatal or paediatric studies were only included if data for the neonatal subset were disaggregated and could be analysed separately. We thereby excluded studies focusing exclusively on outcomes beyond 28 days of life or only on maternal outcomes. We included neonates from any setting (hospital-based or community), in any country income context, recognising that neonatal heat vulnerability is a global concern. We required that the exposure of interest be clearly related to heat (e.g. ambient temperature, heatwaves, or heat indices). Studies without a defined ambient heat exposure or without neonatal outcome data were excluded. By restricting the population and outcomes in this way, we ensured the review's relevance to the neonatal period while not missing any study that specifically examined neonatal outcomes of heat exposure.

^b Resources and templates available from [Scoping Reviews - Resources | JBI](#).

We cast a wide net for relevant evidence, considering all primary research designs addressing our population, exposure, and outcomes of interest. Both observational and experimental study designs were eligible. In practice, most available evidence on heat and neonatal health comes from observational epidemiological studies (e.g. cohort, case-control, time-series, or case-crossover analyses examining temperature exposure and neonatal outcomes). We included these types of studies, as well as any interventional studies (for example, trials of heat mitigation interventions during pregnancy or for newborn care), though we expected such trials to be rare for ethical and logistical reasons.

We also included cross-sectional studies, ecological studies, and case series if they reported relevant quantitative data on heat exposure and neonatal outcomes. Qualitative and mixed-methods studies were included only if they contained an empirical component linking heat exposure to neonatal health—for instance, a qualitative study with some quantitative data on neonatal outcomes in hot conditions. Our primary interest, however, was in quantitative evidence of associations, so any qualitative insights from included studies are used mainly to contextualise the findings rather than as outcome data.

We did not include secondary research such as systematic or scoping reviews as sources of data, to avoid duplication of evidence. Such reviews, if encountered, were checked to ensure we identified all relevant primary studies (backward reference searching), but they were not treated as included studies for data extraction.

Similarly, non-empirical literature – including conference abstracts, editorials, commentaries, and letters – was excluded since these do not provide original data on exposure–outcome relationships.

We aimed to include primarily peer-reviewed and full-text publications meeting our inclusion criteria. All sources ultimately had to meet the same inclusion criteria regarding participants, exposure, and outcomes (shown in Table 2).

Table 2. Review #2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria used for screening

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population: Study includes neonates (0–28 days) or disaggregated neonatal data. Studies done in humans.	Ineligible population: No neonatal data or data not disaggregated. Animal studies.
Exposure: Heat exposure is clearly defined (e.g., ambient temperature, heatwave, heat index).	Ineligible exposure: No clear heat exposure or exposure unrelated to ambient/climatic heat.
Outcome: Reports neonatal outcomes within the first 28 days of life, including but not limited to mortality, preterm birth, low birth weight, neonatal infections (e.g. sepsis), heat-related illness or dehydration, diarrhoea, birth asphyxia, and neonatal intensive care unit admission.	Wrong outcome: Only maternal outcomes or outcomes after 28 days of life.
Design: Primary empirical research (observational, interventional, mixed methods with quantitative data).	Wrong study type: Editorial, opinion, commentary, review, abstract only, or modelling without data.
Context: All settings will be considered, including high-, middle-, and low-income countries, and both urban and rural environments.	
Publication type: Full-text article or eligible grey literature with original data.	Duplicate: Duplicate of another included study.

4.1.2 Search strategy

A comprehensive search strategy was developed in consultation with a research librarian and peer-reviewed following PRESS guidelines. We conducted an initial search of major databases on July 16, 2025. The databases searched were MEDLINE (via PubMed), Embase, and Scopus. The strategy combined terms for heat exposure with terms for neonatal outcomes and additionally explored terms related to climate change to ensure no relevant concepts were missed. For example, we used Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and keywords such as “Hot Temperature,” “Extreme Heat,” and “Heatwave*,” in combination with neonatal outcome terms like “neonatal mortality,” “preterm birth,” and “low birth weight”. We also tested adding climate-change-related terms to see how they narrowed the results.

In developing our strategy, we decided not to restrict the search only to studies explicitly framed as climate change research. While our review is motivated by climate change concerns, imposing a climate-related filter could exclude many studies that examine heat and neonatal outcomes without using climate change keywords. Therefore, we kept the search broad. We applied no language or publication date restrictions at the search stage, aiming to capture all relevant studies. We did not filter out non-English studies during the search; instead, we planned to translate or enlist native speakers for screening and data extraction of non-English articles where possible. If a study in another language met inclusion criteria but could not be translated with available resources, it would be documented and treated as excluded due to language, acknowledging this as a limitation in our review process.

In addition to the database searches, we manually screened the reference lists of all included articles to identify any further studies that our searches might have missed. We also considered contacting authors of included studies for clarifications or missing data when necessary.

4.1.3 Selection process

We used a two-stage screening process (title/abstract screening followed by full-text screening) to identify articles for inclusion. Citations retrieved from the searches were imported into reference management software and then into a systematic review management tool (Rayyan) for screening. Screening was carried out independently by two reviewers. A pilot test of the eligibility criteria was conducted on a random sample of 25 titles and abstracts. Reviewers met to discuss discrepancies and refine the screening approach. In the first phase, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance according to the pre-established inclusion criteria. In the second phase, full-text articles of potentially relevant studies were retrieved and assessed for eligibility. All these steps were conducted and reported in accordance with the PRISMA-ScR checklist.

4.1.4 Data collection process

Data extraction was conducted using a standardised, pre-piloted charting form. This form was tested on a small sample of studies to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness, and includes the domains listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Review #2: Charting form for data extraction for the scoping review

Category	Data items
Study Characteristics	Authors, year of publication, journal, country/region
Study Design	Type of study (e.g., cohort, case-crossover), sample size, study setting
Population	Neonatal population details (age in days, inclusion/exclusion criteria, subgroups like preterm/low birth weight)
Exposure	Type of heat exposure (e.g., ambient temp, heat index, thresholds), measurement source
Exposure window	Duration and timing of exposure (e.g., lag days, trimester, neonatal period)
Outcomes	Neonatal outcomes assessed (e.g., mortality, preterm birth, infections), and outcome definitions
Heat Definition	Metric used (e.g., max temp, mean temp, heatwave criteria), cutoffs/thresholds
Mediators (if extracted)	Only if directly linked to neonatal outcome (e.g., maternal dehydration causing neonatal sepsis)
Key Findings	Direction and strength of association (e.g., odd ratios, relative risks, qualitative findings)
Confounders/Adjustments	Variables adjusted for (e.g., air pollution, socioeconomic status, gestational age)
Quality Flags	If applicable, e.g., major limitations noted by authors or reviewers

This template is consistent with the JBI and PRISMA-ScR guidance, and is adapted from charting frameworks in related reviews by Chersich et al. (2020) and Lakhoo et al. (2025).^{1,3}

Two reviewers performed data extraction independently and discrepancies were resolved through consensus. We did not assess the quality of the studies.

4.2 Results

We screened 8,457 records of which 138 studies were included for assessment (Figure 4) and listed in Appendix B.

Figure 4. Review #2: PRISMA flow diagram representing the results of the screening process

Because we conducted the above updated systematic review #1 almost in parallel, and because we wanted to ‘scope’ if studies reveal other adverse neonatal health outcomes than preterm birth (which was found to be the most studied outcome), we focused our scoping review initially on those studies which were not included in the systematic review updates (n=76) and which did not focus exclusively on

preterm birth (n=25). This ‘exclusion’ resulted in a smaller sample of 37 studies which we assessed preliminary. The 138 studies included in review #2 will be fully assessed and described in the forthcoming review article, but here we only describe the findings of the sub-sample of 37 studies.

Table 4 shows that most of the 37 studies have been published in 2020 or later, and they cover a broad geographic range.

Table 4. Review #2: Distribution of studies across location and time

	Categories	Number of studies	Percentage (%)
Location of Study (Continent)	Africa	6	16
	Asia	10	27
	Australia	1	3
	Europe	9	24
	North America	6	16
	South America	2	5
	Multiple	3	8
Year of Publication	Pre-1980	0	0
	1980-1999	1	2
	2000-2009	1	2
	2010-2019	2	5
	Post-2020	33	89

Asia and Europe together account for about half of the new studies, with substantial contributions from Africa and North America as well. A smaller number of studies were conducted in Australia and South America. Three multi-country studies span multiple continents.

Notably, all but four of the newly added studies were published in 2020 or later, reflecting a recent surge in research on heat and perinatal health outcomes. Only one study was published in the 1980s–1990s and one in the 2000s, both of which were experimental studies, while two were published in the 2010s. The “Post-2020” category comprises roughly 89% of the new studies, underscoring that most evidence in this update comes from very recent literature.

Almost half of the 37 articles focus on low birth weight (n=17), sometimes in combination with small for gestational age (n=8). Neonatal mortality is studied less (n=6) and other outcomes, such as newborn wellbeing, feeding difficulties, sleep disturbance, dehydration risk, skin rashes are only mentioned in multi-outcome papers. In addition to this subsample, we must not forget the 25 studies that focus exclusively on preterm birth, but which we excluded from our preliminary review.

4.3 Discussion

This scoping review complements the updated systematic review (review #1) by deliberately targeting studies that explore the effects of heat on neonatal health outcomes. Our preliminary analysis confirms the strong associations between heat exposure and adverse neonatal health outcomes like preterm birth, low birth weight, and small for gestational age. Identification of less commonly studied outcomes (e.g., dehydration risk) points to emerging areas of concern that merit deeper investigation. Adding additional terms to our search strategy could potentially identify more of these or other adverse neonatal health outcomes.

We considered to expand this scoping review on neonatal health outcomes to child (under 5) health outcomes, but a scoping review about the impact of extreme heat and heatwaves on children's health by Schapiro et al (2024) confirmed that the “most robust evidence gleaned from our review pertains to neonates, where studies consistently demonstrate significant associations between extreme heat and adverse birth outcomes such as preterm birth, stillbirth, and low birth weight.²⁰ Their scoping review covers from birth to childhood (up to age < 18) and found – apart from the ‘known’ neonatal health outcomes – a variety of other outcomes, such as increased rates among children of emergency department visits, asthma exacerbations, heat illness, and impaired school performance. Their findings demonstrate that an expansion of our search strategy on neonatal health outcomes to children’s health is most likely not necessary, and also justify why

conducting a systematic review on newborn and child health outcomes at this time may not yet yield additional knowledge given the state of the literature.

5 Conclusion

The evidence of heat exposure effects on pregnancy and birth outcomes is strong and still growing, with preterm birth, low birth weight, small for gestational age, hypertension in pregnancy, congenital abnormalities and stillbirths accounting for most of the evidence. These findings probably underscore the need to refine the search strategy to better capture underrepresented outcomes in future reviews.

We will describe the findings of our scoping review (review #2) in a (forthcoming) publication. The results of the updated systematic review (review #1) will be integrated into deliverable D2.5 - Heat-health attribution report, due February 2026.

6 Appendices

6.1 Appendix A: Study references of **review #1**

Table 5. Review #1: References included in the updated systematic review of heat and maternal and neonatal health outcomes

Main author	Year	Title
Alterman (2024)	2024	Ambient temperature exposure and rapid infant weight gain.
Bonell (2024)	2024	Effect of heat stress in the first 1000 days of life on foetal and infant growth: a secondary analysis of the ENID randomised controlled trial.
Bruckner (2024)	2024	Climate Change and Congenital Anomalies: A Population-Based Study of the Effect of Prolonged Extreme Heat Exposure on the Risk of Neural Tube Defects in France.
Darrow (2024)	2024	Preterm and Early-Term Delivery After Heat Waves in 50 US Metropolitan Areas.
Das (2023)	2023	The risk of miscarriage is associated with ambient temperature: evidence from coastal Bangladesh.
Doyle (2023)	2023	Seasonal patterns in newborns' health: Quantifying the roles of climate, communicable disease, economic and social factors.
Essers (2024)	2024	Ambient air temperature exposure and foetal size and growth in three European birth cohorts.
Gebremedhin (2024)	2024	Maternal exposure to bioclimatic stress and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in Western Australia: identifying potential critical windows of susceptibility.
Guo (2023)	2023	Disparities of Heatwave-Related Preterm Birth in Climate Types - China, 2012-2019.
Guo (2023)	2023	Association of Daytime-Only, Nighttime-Only, and Compound Heat Waves With Preterm Birth by Urban-Rural Area and Regional Socioeconomic Status in China.
Hanson (2024)	2024	A time-stratified, case-crossover study of heat exposure and perinatal mortality from 16 hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa.
Kc (2024)	2024	Effect of non-optimal ambient temperature on preterm birth stratified by social positioning in Nepal: A space-time-stratified case-crossover study.
LaPointe (2024)	2024	Impact of cash transfers on the association between prenatal exposures to high temperatures and low birthweight: Retrospective analysis from the LEAP 1000 study.
LaPointe (2024)	2024	Associations between exposure to extreme ambient heat and neural tube defects in Georgia, USA: A population-based case-control study.
Lin (2023)	2023	Impact of ambient temperature on adverse pregnancy outcomes: a birth cohort study in Fuzhou, China.

Main author	Year	Title
Min (2024)	2024	Disparities in the association between ambient temperature and preterm birth according to individual and regional characteristics: a nationwide time-stratified case-crossover study.
Moodley (2024)	2024	Maternal exposure to heat and its association with miscarriage in rural KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa: A population-based cohort study.
Nyadanu (2024)	2024	Identifying critical periods of susceptibility for maternal exposure to biothermal stress and the risks of stillbirth and spontaneous preterm birth in Western Australia.
Qian (2023)	2023	Influence of temperature on the risk of gestational diabetes mellitus and hypertension in different pregnancy trimesters.
Qiu (2023)	2023	Extreme temperature exposure increases the risk of preterm birth in women with abnormal pre-pregnancy body mass index: a cohort study in a southern province of China.
Rancire (2024)	2024	Associations between heat wave during pregnancy and term birth weight outcomes: The PARIS birth cohort.
Reddam (2024)	2024	Prenatal Exposure to Heat and Humidity and Infant Birth Size in Ghana.
Ren (2023)	2023	Exploration of the preterm birth risk-related heat event thresholds for pregnant women: a population-based cohort study in China.
Runkle (2024)	2024	Association of Psychiatric Emergency Visits and Warm Ambient Temperature during Pregnancy: A Time-Stratified Case-Crossover Study.
Shankar (2023)	2023	Associations between ambient temperature and pregnancy outcomes from three south Asian sites of the Global Network Maternal Newborn Health Registry: A retrospective cohort study.
Wang (2023)	2023	Effects of gestational ambient extreme temperature exposures on the risk of preterm birth in China: A sibling-matched study based on a multi-centre prospective cohort.
Wang (2024)	2024	Increased risk of preterm birth due to heat exposure during pregnancy: Exploring the mechanism of foetal physiology.
Ye (2024)	2024	Heat Exposure, Preterm Birth, and the Role of Greenness in Australia.
Youssim (2023)	2023	Ambient temperature and preeclampsia: A historical cohort study.
Yzen (2023)	2023	Increased late preterm birth risk and altered uterine blood flow upon exposure to heat stress.
Zeng (2024)	2024	Association of air temperature exposure during pregnancy with risk of preeclampsia in Guangzhou, China.

6.2 Appendix B: Study references of review #2

Table 6. Review #2: References included in the scoping review of heat and neonatal health outcomes

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Reddam, A.	2025	Prenatal exposure to heat and humidity and infant birth size in Ghana	10.1016/j.envres.2024.120557
Hanson, C.	2024	A time-stratified, case-crossover study of heat exposure and perinatal mortality from 16 hospitals in sub-Saharan Africa	10.1038/s41591-024-03245-7
Bruckner, T.	2024	Climate Change and Congenital Anomalies: A Population-Based Study of the Effect of Prolonged Extreme Heat Exposure on the Risk of Neural Tube Defects in France	10.1002/bdr2.2397
Rancire, F.	2024	Associations between heat wave during pregnancy and term birth weight outcomes: The PARIS birth cohort	10.1016/j.envint.2024.108730
LaPointe, S.	2024	Impact of cash transfers on the association between prenatal exposures to high temperatures and low birthweight: Retrospective analysis from the LEAP 1000 study	10.1111/1471-0528.17761
Min, J.	2024	Disparities in the association between ambient temperature and preterm birth according to individual and regional characteristics: a nationwide time-stratified case-crossover study	10.1186/s12940-024-01062-6
Kc, A.	2024	Effect of non-optimal ambient temperature on preterm birth stratified by social positioning in Nepal: A space-time-stratified case-crossover study	10.1016/j.envres.2024.119501
Darrow, L.A.	2024	Preterm and Early-Term Delivery After Heat Waves in 50 US Metropolitan Areas	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.12055
Wang, L.	2024	Increased risk of preterm birth due to heat exposure during pregnancy: Exploring the mechanism of foetal physiology	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172730
Zhang, Y.	2023	Ambient temperature and major structural anomalies: A retrospective study of over 2 million newborns	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.163613
Yzen, D.	2023	Increased late preterm birth risk and altered uterine blood flow upon exposure to heat stress	10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104651
Wang, Q.	2023	Effects of gestational ambient extreme temperature exposures on the risk of preterm birth in China: A sibling-matched study based on a multi-centre prospective cohort	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164135
Li, X.	2023	The relationship between extreme ambient temperature and small for gestational age: A cohort study of 1,436,480 singleton term births in China	10.1016/j.envres.2023.116412
Leung, M.	2023	Ambient temperature during pregnancy and foetal growth in Eastern Massachusetts, USA.	10.1093/ije/dyac228
Shankar, K.	2023	Associations between ambient temperature and pregnancy outcomes from three south Asian sites of the Global Network Maternal Newborn Health Registry: A retrospective cohort study	10.1111/1471-0528.17616

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Guo, Y.	2023	Disparities of Heatwave-Related Preterm Birth in Climate Types — China, 2012–2019	10.46234/ccdcw2023.205
Guo, Y.	2023	Association of Daytime-Only, Nighttime-Only, and Compound Heat Waves with Preterm Birth by Urban-Rural Area and Regional Socioeconomic Status in China	10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2023.26987
Qiu, J.	2023	Extreme temperature exposure increases the risk of preterm birth in women with abnormal pre-pregnancy body mass index: a cohort study in a southern province of China	10.3389/fpubh.2023.1156880
Conte Keivabu, R.	2022	Extreme Heat, Birth Outcomes, and Socioeconomic Heterogeneity	10.1215/00703370-10174836 LK
Cil, G.	2022	Extreme temperatures during pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: Evidence from 2009 to 2018 U.S. national birth data	10.1002/hec.4559
de Bont, J.	2022	Associations between ambient temperature and risk of preterm birth in Sweden: A comparison of analytical approaches	10.1016/j.envres.2022.113586
Zhang, Y.	2022	The burden of heatwave-related preterm births and associated human capital losses in China	10.1038/s41467-022-35008-8
Bakhtsiyarava, M.	2022	Ambient temperature and term birthweight in Latin American cities	10.1016/j.envint.2022.107412
Requia, W.J.	2022	The association of maternal exposure to ambient temperature with low birth weight in term pregnancies varies by location: In Brazil, positive associations may occur only in the Amazon region	10.1016/j.envres.2022.113923
Nyadanu, S.D.	2022	Prenatal acute thermophysiological stress and spontaneous preterm birth in Western Australia, 2000–2015: A space-time-stratified case-crossover analysis	10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.114029
McElroy, S.	2022	Extreme heat, preterm birth, and stillbirth: A global analysis across 14 lower-middle income countries	10.1016/j.envint.2021.106902
Cushing, L.	2022	Extreme heat and its association with social disparities in the risk of spontaneous preterm birth	10.1111/ppe.12834
Jegasothy, E.	2022	Maternal factors and risk of spontaneous preterm birth due to high ambient temperatures in New South Wales, Australia	10.1111/ppe.12822
Tapia, V.L.	2021	Association between maximum temperature and PM2.5with pregnancy outcomes in Lima, Peru	10.1097/EE9.000000000000179
Dastoorpoor, M.	2021	Association between Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) with adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, southwest of Iran	10.1186/s12884-021-03876-5
Yang, D.	2021	Influence of ambient temperature and diurnal temperature variation on the premature rupture of membranes in East China: A distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis	10.1016/j.envres.2021.111145
Basagaña, X.	2021	Low and high ambient temperatures during pregnancy and birth weight among 624,940 singleton term births in Israel (2010–2014): An investigation of potential windows of susceptibility	10.1289/EHP8117
Cheng, P.	2021	Short-term effects of ambient temperature on preterm birth: a time-series analysis in Xuzhou, China	10.1007/s11356-020-11201-4

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Li, C.	2021	Temperature variation and preterm birth among live singleton deliveries in Shenzhen, China: A time-to-event analysis	10.1016/j.envres.2021.110834
Tang, Z.	2021	Impact of ambient temperature exposure on newborns with low Apgar scores in northwest China	10.1007/s11356-021-13340-8
Kwag, Y.	2021	Effect of heat waves and fine particulate matter on preterm births in Korea from 2010 to 2016	10.1016/j.envint.2020.106239
Lawrence, W.R.	2021	A population-based case-control study of the association between weather-related extreme heat events and low birthweight	10.1017/S2040174420000392
Smith, M.L.	2020	Association of summer heat waves and the probability of preterm birth in Minnesota: An exploration of the intersection of race and education	10.3390/ijerph17176391
Wang, Y.-Y.	2020	Ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth: A national birth cohort study in the mainland China	10.1016/j.envint.2020.105851
Wang, Q.	2020	Independent and combined effects of heatwaves and PM2.5 on preterm birth in Guangzhou, China: A survival analysis	10.1289/EHP5117
Ilango, S.D.	2020	Extreme heat episodes and risk of preterm birth in California, 2005–2013	10.1016/j.envint.2020.105541
Liu, X.	2020	Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the risk of preterm birth and the effect modification of birth order during the new baby boom: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China	10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113481
Gronlund, C.J.	2020	Time series analysis of total and direct associations between high temperatures and preterm births in Detroit, Michigan	10.1136/bmjopen-2019-032476
Wang, J.	2019	Exposure to heat wave during pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: An exploration of susceptible windows	10.1097/EDE.0000000000000995
Son, J.-Y.	2019	Impacts of high temperature on adverse birth outcomes in Seoul, Korea: Disparities by individual- and community-level characteristics	10.1016/j.envres.2018.10.032
Mohammadi, D.	2019	Environmental extreme temperature and daily preterm birth in Sabzevar, Iran: A time-series analysis	10.1186/s12199-018-0760-x
Sun, S.	2019	Ambient temperature and preterm birth: A retrospective study of 32 million US singleton births	10.1016/j.envint.2019.02.023
Basu, R.	2018	Temperature and Term Low Birth Weight in California	10.1093/aje/kwy116
Zhong, Q.	2018	Preterm birth and ambient temperature: Strong association during night-time and warm seasons	10.1016/j.jtherbio.2018.11.002
Li, S.	2018	Exploring associations of maternal exposure to ambient temperature with duration of gestation and birth weight: A prospective study	10.1186/s12884-018-2100-y
Li, S.	2018	Temporal change in the impacts of ambient temperature on preterm birth and stillbirth: Brisbane, 1994–2013	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.03.385

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Zheng, X.	2018	An epidemiological assessment of the effect of ambient temperature on the incidence of preterm births: Identifying windows of susceptibility during pregnancy	10.1016/j.jtherbio.2018.04.001
Guo, T.	2018	The association between ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth in China	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.09.104
Walfisch, A.	2017	Trends, seasonality and effect of ambient temperature on preterm delivery	10.1080/14767058.2016.1253063
Cil, G.	2017	Potential Climate Change Health Risks from Increases in Heat Waves: Abnormal Birth Outcomes and Adverse Maternal Health Conditions	10.1111/risa.12767
Avalos, L.A.	2017	The impact of high apparent temperature on spontaneous preterm delivery: a case-crossover study	10.1186/s12940-017-0209-5
Mathew, S.	2017	Examining the effects of ambient temperature on preterm birth in Central Australia	10.3390/ijerph14020147
Auger, N.	2017	Elevated outdoor temperatures and risk of stillbirth	10.1093/ije/dyw077
Basu, R.	2017	The impact of maternal factors on the association between temperature and preterm delivery	10.1016/j.envres.2016.12.017
Kilinc, M.F.	2016	Does maternal exposure during pregnancy to higher ambient temperature increase the risk of hypospadias?	10.1016/j.jpuro.2016.06.015
Cox, B.	2016	Ambient temperature as a trigger of preterm delivery in a temperate climate	10.1136/jech-2015-206384
Liang, Z.	2016	The association between ambient temperature and preterm birth in Shenzhen, China: A distributed lag non-linear time series analysis	10.1186/s12940-016-0166-4
He, J.-R.	2016	Ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth in Guangzhou, China (2001-2011)	10.1289/ehp.1509778
Basu, R.	2016	Association between high ambient temperature and risk of stillbirth in California	10.1093/aje/kww295
Arroyo, V.	2016	Short term effect of air pollution, noise and heat waves on preterm births in Madrid (Spain)	10.1016/j.envres.2015.11.034
Poeran, J.	2016	The Impact of Extremes in Outdoor Temperature and Sunshine Exposure on Birth Weight	PMID: 26867297
Schifano, P.	2016	Heat and air pollution exposure as triggers of delivery: A survival analysis of population-based pregnancy cohorts in Rome and Barcelona	10.1016/j.envint.2015.12.013
Ngo, N.S.	2016	Climate change and foetal health: The impacts of exposure to extreme temperatures in New York City	10.1016/j.envres.2015.11.016
Vicedo-Cabrera, A.M.	2015	Exposure to seasonal temperatures during the last month of gestation and the risk of preterm birth in Stockholm	10.3390/ijerph120403962
Kakkad, K.	2014	Neonates in Ahmedabad, India, during the 2010 Heat Wave: A climate change adaptation study	10.1155/2014/946875
Vicedo-Cabrera, A.M.	2014	Exposure to elevated temperatures and risk of preterm birth in Valencia, Spain	10.1016/j.envres.2014.07.021

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Auger, N.	2014	Extreme heat and risk of early delivery among preterm and term pregnancies	10.1097/EDE.0000000000000074
Wang, J.	2013	Maternal exposure to heatwave and preterm birth in Brisbane, Australia	10.1111/1471-0528.12397
Schifano, P.	2013	Effect of ambient temperature and air pollutants on the risk of preterm birth, Rome 2001-2010	10.1016/j.envint.2013.09.005
van Zutphen, A.R.	2012	A population-based case-control study of extreme summer temperature and birth defects	10.1289/ehp.1104671
Wells, J.C.K.	2002	Birth weight and environmental heat load: A between-population analysis	10.1002/ajpa.10137 LK
Lusambili, A.	2025	Reducing Extreme Heat Impacts on Health in Pregnant Women and Infants: a community based intervention in Kilifi, Kenya	10.1093/heapol/czaf028 LK
Del Carretto, M.	2025	Short-term ambient heat exposure and low APGAR score in newborns: A time-stratified case-crossover analysis in São Paulo state, Brazil (2013-2019)	10.1101/2025.04.08.25325468 LK
Fatima, S.H.	2025	Disproportionate Climate Burden of Rising Temperature on Low Birth Weights in a Health-Compromised Nation	10.2139/ssrn.5116051 LK
Yuan, X.	2025	The association of apparent temperature with foetal growth: A birth cohort study in Beijing, China	10.1016/j.scs.2025.106266
Ma, Y.	2025	The modifying role of residential greenness on the association between heat waves and adverse birth outcomes: Results from the ELEFANT project	10.1016/j.envres.2025.121118
Khalili, R.	2025	Adverse Birth Outcomes Associated with Heat Stress and Wildfire Smoke Exposure During Preconception and Pregnancy	10.1021/acs.est.4c10194
Ngongo, C.J.	2025	Country-level impact of climate change on maternal and newborn health: Associations between temperature, precipitation, maternal mortality, stillbirth, and neonatal mortality in the Democratic Republic of the Congo	10.1016/j.envint.2025.109564
Ai, S.	2025	Assessing the association between prenatal ambient temperature and extreme low birth weight in South Asia	10.1016/j.ijheh.2025.114593
Jung, D.	2025	The Association between Extreme Temperatures and Birth Weight in South Korea	10.1175/WCAS-D-24-0020.1
Cebolla-Boado, H.	2025	Birth weight in a warming world: investigating the protective role of the “healthy immigrant effect” against extreme heat	10.1007/s11111-025-00482-x
Campero, M.	2025	Environmental Factors Linked to Birth Outcomes in Urban Localities Across Argentina	10.1111/cch.70054
Hong, Y.	2025	Heat and humidity on early-life outcomes: Evidence from Mexico	10.1016/j.jjeem.2024.103082
d’Errico, A.	2025	Maternal occupational exposures during early stages of pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes in the NINFEA birth-cohort	10.1371/journal.pone.0313085
Lusambili, A.	2025	Too hot to thrive: a qualitative inquiry of community perspectives on the effect of high ambient temperature on postpartum women and neonates in Kilifi, Kenya	10.1186/s12887-023-04517-w

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Shaw, S.	2025	The association of temperature extremes, ecosystem resilience, with child mortality: Novel evidence from India	10.1016/j.envres.2024.120690
Burgos-Ochoa, L.	2025	Health disparities in the impact of prenatal temperature exposure on birth outcomes: A nationwide population-based study in the Netherlands	10.1016/j.puhe.2025.105819
Hira Fatima, S.	2025	Impact of extreme ambient temperatures on low birth weight: Insights from empirical findings in Pakistan	10.1177/17455057251341723
Brimicombe, C.	2025	The influence of heat exposure on birth and neonatal outcomes in Mombasa, Kenya: A pooled time series analysis	10.1016/j.joclim.2024.100409
Zhu, Z.	2024	Estimating the burden of temperature-related low birthweight attributable to anthropogenic climate change in low-income and middle-income countries: a retrospective, multicentre, epidemiological study	10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00242-0
Manfredini, M.	2024	Not only cold but also heat: the effect of maternal exposure to high temperatures during gestation on neonatal mortality in pre-transitional Casalguidi, 1819–1859	10.1007/s11111-024-00467-2
Dimitrova, A.	2024	Temperature-related neonatal deaths attributable to climate change in 29 low- and middle-income countries	10.1038/s41467-024-49890-x
LaPointe, S.	2024	Exposure to acute ambient temperature extremes and neonatal intensive care unit admissions: A case-crossover study	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176149
Huang, Z.	2024	Associations between PM2.5, ambient heat exposure and congenital hydronephrosis in southeastern China	10.3389/fpubh.2024.1389969
Rekha, S.	2024	Heat stress and adverse pregnancy outcome: Prospective cohort study	10.1111/1471-0528.17680
Nyadanu, S.D.	2024	Identifying critical periods of susceptibility for maternal exposure to biothermal stress and the risks of stillbirth and spontaneous preterm birth in Western Australia.	10.1093/aje/kwae431
Carlson, J.M.	2023	Critical windows of susceptibility for the effects of prenatal exposure to heat and heat variability on gestational growth	10.1016/j.envres.2022.114607
Chen, J.	2023	Modification effects of ambient temperature on associations of ambient ozone exposure before and during pregnancy with adverse birth outcomes: A multicity study in China	10.1016/j.envint.2023.107791
Wang, P.	2023	Temperature variability and birthweight: Epidemiological evidence from Africa	10.1016/j.envint.2023.107792
Jiao, A.	2023	The role of extreme heat exposure on premature rupture of membranes in Southern California: A study from a large pregnancy cohort	10.1016/j.envint.2023.107824
Karlsson, L.	2021	Socioeconomic disparities in climate vulnerability: neonatal mortality in northern Sweden, 1880–1950	10.1007/s11111-021-00383-9
Hajdu, T.	2021	Temperature, climate change, and birth weight: evidence from Hungary	10.1007/s11111-021-00380-y
Blavier, F.	2021	Effect of air temperature on human births, preterm births and births associated with maternal hypertension	10.1080/14767058.2021.1919075

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Junkka, J.	2021	Climate vulnerability of Swedish newborns: Gender differences and time trends of temperature-related neonatal mortality, 1880–1950	10.1016/j.envres.2020.110400
Zhang, W.	2019	Projected changes in maternal heat exposure during early pregnancy and the associated congenital heart defect burden in the united states	10.1161/JAHA.118.010995
MacVicar, S.	2017	How seasonality and weather affect perinatal health: Comparing the experiences of indigenous and non-indigenous mothers in Kanungu District, Uganda	10.1016/j.socscimed.2017.06.021
Simbruner, G.	2005	Premature infants are less capable of maintaining thermal balance of head and body with increases of thermal environment than with decreases	10.1055/s-2004-837265
Vaha-Eskeli, K.	1990	The effect of short-term heat stress on uterine contractility, foetal heart rate and foetal movements at late pregnancy	10.1016/0028-2243(91)90200-5.
Fitch, A.	2025	Preterm and early-term delivery after heat waves in eight US states: A case-crossover study using the High-resolution Urban Meteorology for Impacts Dataset (HUMID)	10.1101/2025.03.04.25323373LK
Wang, Y.	2025	Extreme urban temperature exposure and preterm birth: Spatial-temporal risk zone prediction using machine learning models	10.1016/j.envres.2025.122230
Girgin, S.	2025	Prenatal exposure to ambient temperature and preterm birth: A historical cohort	10.1093/ije/dyaf106
Li, Y.	2025	Projecting future disease and economic burdens of heatwave-related preterm birth in China under different climate scenarios	10.1016/j.envint.2025.109608
Huang, Q.	2025	Maternal exposure to ambient temperature and risk of preterm birth in Chengdu, China, from 2017 to 2020: a cohort study	10.1186/s12889-025-21403-5
Lin, S.	2025	Identifying county-level effect modifiers of the association between heat waves and preterm birth using a Bayesian spatial meta regression approach.	10.1101/2025.07.03.25330695
Ha, S.	2024	Impacts of heat and wildfire on preterm birth	10.1016/j.envres.2024.119094
Wang, L.	2024	Heat exposure induced risks of preterm birth mediated by maternal hypertension	10.1038/s41591-024-03002-w
Terada, S.	2024	Ambient temperature and preterm birth: A case-crossover study	10.1111/1471-0528.17720
Ye, T.	2024	Heat Exposure, Preterm Birth, and the Role of Greenness in Australia	10.1001/jamapediatrics.2024.0001
Gordon, M.	2023	Disparities in preterm birth following the July 1995 Chicago heat wave	10.1016/j.annepidem.2023.08.008
Ren, M.	2023	Exploration of the preterm birth risk-related heat event thresholds for pregnant women: a population-based cohort study in China	10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100785
Yu, G.	2023	Extreme Temperature Exposure and Risks of Preterm Birth Subtypes Based on a Nationwide Survey in China	10.1289/EHP10831

Main Author	Year	Study Title	DOI
Xiao, X.	2023	Evidence of interactive effects of late-pregnancy exposure to air pollution and extreme temperature on preterm birth in China: A nationwide study	10.1088/1748-9326/aceb0b
Wu, Y.	2023	Effects of ambient temperature and relative humidity on preterm birth during early pregnancy and before parturition in China from 2010 to 2018: a population-based large-sample cohort study	10.3389/fpubh.2023.1101283
Singh, T.	2023	Acute air pollution and temperature exposure as independent and joint triggers of spontaneous preterm birth in New South Wales, Australia: a time-to-event analysis	10.3389/fpubh.2023.1220797
Zhang, H.	2023	Interaction effects of night-time temperature and PM2.5 on preterm birth in Huai River Basin, China	10.1016/j.envint.2023.107729
Ren, M.	2022	Effects of extreme temperature on the risk of preterm birth in China: A population-based multi-centre cohort study	10.1016/j.lanwpc.2022.100496
Son, J.-Y.	2022	Exposure to heat during pregnancy and preterm birth in North Carolina: Main effect and disparities by residential greenness, urbanicity, and socioeconomic status	10.1016/j.envres.2021.112315
Ranjbaran, M.	2022	Ambient temperature and air pollution, and the risk of preterm birth in Tehran, Iran: a time series study	10.1080/14767058.2020.1731458
Huang, M.	2021	Acute associations between heatwaves and preterm and early-term birth in 50 US metropolitan areas: a matched case-control study	10.1186/s12940-021-00733-y
Vilcins, D.	2021	The Association of Ambient Temperature with Extremely Preterm Births	10.1007/s10995-021-03203-6
Zhou, G.	2021	Preconception ambient temperature and preterm birth: a time-series study in rural Henan, China	10.1007/s11356-020-11457-w
Sun, Y.	2020	Examining the joint effects of heatwaves, air pollution, and green space on the risk of preterm birth in California	10.1088/1748-9326/abb8a3
Asta, F.	2019	The modifying role of socioeconomic position and greenness on the short-term effect of heat and air pollution on preterm births in Rome, 2001–2013	10.3390/ijerph16142497

7 References

- ¹ Chersich MF, Pham MD, Areal A, Haghghi MM, Manyuchi A, Swift CP, et al. Associations between high temperatures in pregnancy and risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirths: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *The BMJ*. 2020 Nov 4;371.
- ² Lakhoo DP, Brink N, Wise A, Solarin I, Luchters S, Craig M, et al. HIGH Horizons - High temperature exposure in pregnancy and adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Zenodo; 2024 Jul. <https://zenodo.org/records/12779149>
- ³ Lakhoo DP, Brink N, Radebe L, Craig MH, Pham MD, Haghghi MM, Wise A, Solarin I, Luchters S, Maimela G, Chersich MF; Heat-Health Study Group; HIGH Horizons Study Group. A systematic review and meta-analysis of heat exposure impacts on maternal, foetal and neonatal health. *Nat Med*. 2024. doi: 10.1038/s41591-024-03395-8.
- ⁴ IPCC. Impacts of 1.5°C Global Warming on Natural and Human Systems. In: *Global Warming of 15°C*. Cambridge University Press; 2022. p. 175–312.
- ⁵ Gallo E, Quijal-Zamorano M, Méndez Turrubiates RF, Tonne C, Basagaña X, Achebak H, et al. Heat-related mortality in Europe during 2023 and the role of adaptation in protecting health. *Nat Med*. 2024 Nov 1
- ⁶ Scorgie F, Lusambili A, Luchters S, Khaemba P, Filippi V, Nakstad B, et al. “Mothers get really exhausted!” The lived experience of pregnancy in extreme heat: Qualitative findings from Kilifi, Kenya. *Soc Sci Med*. 2023 Oct 1;335.
- ⁷ Chersich MF, Pham MD, Areal A, Haghghi MM, Manyuchi A, Swift CP, et al. Associations between high temperatures in pregnancy and risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirths: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *The BMJ*. 2020 Nov 4;371.
- ⁸ van Daalen KR, Tonne C, Semenza JC, Rocklöv J, Markandya A, Dasandi N, et al. The 2024 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: unprecedented warming demands unprecedented action. Vol. 9, *The Lancet Public Health*. Elsevier Ltd; 2024. p. e495–522.
- ⁹ Giudice LC, Llamas-Clark EF, DeNicola N, Pandipati S, Zlatnik MG, Decena DCD, et al. Climate change, women’s health, and the role of obstetricians and gynaecologists in leadership. *International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics*. 2021 Dec 1;155(3):345–56.
- ¹⁰ Ebi KL, Capon A, Berry P, Broderick C, de Dear R, Havenith G, et al. Hot weather and heat extremes: health risks. Vol. 398, *The Lancet*. Elsevier B.V.; 2021. p. 698–708.
- ¹¹ Amadi HO. Neonatal Thermoneutrality in a Tropical Climate. *Current Topics in Tropical Medicine*. InTech; 2012

- ¹² Trevisanuto D, Testoni D, de Almeida MFB. Maintaining normothermia: Why and how? *Semin Foetal Neonatal Med.* 2018 Oct 1;23(5):333–9.
- ¹³ Dimitrova A, Dimitrova A, Mengel M, Gasparrini A, Lotze-Campen H, Gabrysch S. Temperature-related neonatal deaths attributable to climate change in 29 low- and middle-income countries. *Nat Commun.* 2024 Dec 1;15(1).
- ¹⁴ Dalugoda Y, Kuppa J, Phung H, Rutherford S, Phung D. Effect of Elevated Ambient Temperature on Maternal, Foetal, and Neonatal Outcomes: A Scoping Review. Vol. 19, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.* MDPI; 2022.
- ¹⁵ Nyadanu SD, Dunne J, Tessema GA, Mullins B, Kumi-Boateng B, Bell ML, et al. Maternal exposure to ambient air temperature and adverse birth outcomes: An umbrella review of systematic reviews and meta-analyses. Vol. 917, *Science of the Total Environment.* Elsevier B.V.; 2024.
- ¹⁶ Nakstad B, Filippi V, Lusambili A, Roos N, Scorgie F, Chersich MF, et al. How Climate Change May Threaten Progress in Neonatal Health in the African Region. *Neonatology.* 2022 Oct 1;119(5):644–51.
- ¹⁷ Bonell A, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Moirano G, Sonko B, Jeffries D, Moore SE, et al. Effect of heat stress in the first 1000 days of life on foetal and infant growth: a secondary analysis of the ENID randomised controlled trial. *Lancet Planet Health.* 2024 Oct 1;8(10):e734–43.
- ¹⁸ Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Syst Rev.* 2021;10(1):89.
- ¹⁹ Tricco, AC, Lillie, E, Zarin, W, O'Brien, KK, Colquhoun, H, Levac, D, Moher, D, Peters, MD, Horsley, T, Weeks, L, Hempel, S et al. PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018,169(7):467-473. doi: 10.7326/M18-0850
- ²⁰ Schapiro LH, McShane MA, Marwah HK, Callaghan ME, Neudecker ML. Impact of extreme heat and heatwaves on children's health: A scoping review. *The Journal of Climate Change and Health*, Volume 19, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2024.100335>.